

Practical Aspects Of Preparing Future Teachers For Professional Socialization Of Students

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Annotation. This article covers the practical aspects of preparing future teachers for professional socialization of students. The article also presents opinions on the choice of profession and its pedagogical and psychological aspects, the main tasks of preparing future teachers for professional socialization of students.

Keywords. Profession, future teacher, professional activity, pedagogical opportunity, decision, development

INTRODUCTION

Today, the issues of guiding young people towards a profession and increasing the role of teachers in this regard are becoming increasingly urgent.

Choosing a profession is one of the most important decisions in the life of every person. A profession is a source of income, and at the same time, an activity that makes up a large part of one's life. Psychologists recommend analyzing other opportunities when making such important decisions, instead of relying solely on the advice of those around them. "From the point of view of the psychology of professional socialization, the following are recommended:

1. Psychological tests. A person's interest and inclinations to a profession can be determined at the initial stage through psychological tests. However, such tests should be based not only on the options available on online platforms, but on professional tests developed by industry experts. It is inappropriate to view the test results as a "verdict"; they only serve as an auxiliary tool in determining the direction of inclination.

2. Expanding knowledge about professions. It is important to consolidate knowledge about various professional areas, promising areas and specialties. Every year, new books are published on the professional socialization of students. These

books provide even schoolchildren with the opportunity to get acquainted with professions that are unfamiliar to them.

3. Get to know professions in detail. On the eve of graduating from school, teenagers often have the wrong ideas about professions. They see only the positive or, conversely, the negative aspects of their chosen professions. In this case, parents need to help their children clarify many things. Starting from the 9th grade, it is recommended to participate in "Open Doors" days at institutes and universities in order to gradually get acquainted with their chosen direction.

4. Systematize desires. It is recommended to place the professions that interest you vertically and what you expect from the chosen profession horizontally. It is advisable to fill out the table in as much detail as possible. If the chosen profession and the requirements expected from it coincide, you should put a "+" sign, otherwise a "-" sign. This method helps to clarify desires and allows you to form a clear idea of the professions that correspond to these desires.

5. Practice. After making a decision on the chosen profession, you should try your hand at it in that direction.

6. Backup choice. In addition to the main choice, it is also necessary to consider the "backup" choice, which is considered additionally. Because it

is impossible to accurately predict life in advance, and various situations are likely to arise. In order not to be discouraged if you do not get into the chosen direction, it is useful to consider other alternative options.

7. The decision is made only independently. Parental advice can be useful, but it is advisable that it should not be taken as a final decision, but only play a supporting role. It is also wrong for parents to direct their child to a profession that they did not achieve in their youth, but which has become a dream. A child is an independent person and has his own desires. These desires should not be sacrificed for desires that were previously a dream.

8. Continuing family traditions is not mandatory. If a child wants to continue the profession of his father or mother, this is a very positive situation. But forcing him to do this is not worth it. The fact that the father found his happiness and success in that profession does not mean that the son will also achieve the same result. If a person is engaged in a job he does not like all his life, he feels unhappy. [1.P.32]

One of the main functions of a general secondary school is to clearly and clearly reveal the unique aspects of each student. In this process, it is necessary to develop students culturally and morally, instill in them qualities such as self-sacrifice, a positive outlook, respect for oneself and others, and a desire for creativity. The uniqueness of each student determines the direction of his development. This, in turn, creates an opportunity to determine their own direction of activity in a general secondary educational institution. Students acquire the skills to clearly imagine and evaluate the results of their activities. As a result, they develop self-confidence and motivation to strive for new achievements. [2.P.117-120]

Preparing future teachers for the activities of professional socialization of students performs another important function, namely, eliminating or

minimizing the contradictions that arise between the objective needs of society for personnel and the subjective professional desires and aspirations of young people formed over the years, the opinions of young people based on insufficient knowledge of modern professions and trends in the labor market and the choice of a profession based on old stereotypes. [3.P.200]

The main tasks of preparing future teachers for the professional socialization of students are: “providing professional information; providing students with an understanding of the types of modern production, the labor market, and information about the requirements that professions place on people; creating the basis for providing information about vocational education institutions. Professional socialization of students has the following structural structure”:

1. When developing mechanisms for organizing high-quality professional recommendations, it is important to take into account the interests, inclinations, innate abilities, skills, family circumstances, regional opportunities, as well as the desires and goals of students and parents, and the requirements for the profession.

2. It is important to make a final diagnosis, taking into account the individual psychological and physiological characteristics of the person, age, level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as to determine the professional inclinations of the student and assess the degree of orientation of the person. The analysis materials are kept confidential and are discussed only with the student and his parents.

3. In the process of professional socialization, based on the results of psychological, psychophysiological and medical analysis, it is important to provide recommendations on areas of professional training that correspond to the psychological, physiological and psychophysiological characteristics of the person. It

is necessary to help students choose professions that correspond to their interests, abilities and health, in accordance with the needs of society and the requirements of the labor market, as well as to determine the suitability of the person for the chosen profession based on established regulatory requirements.

4. In the process of professional adaptation, it is important to organize a system of measures that will ensure the adaptation of a person to the specialty, the development of social and professional qualities, active creative work, the fulfillment of established requirements and instructions, and the acquisition of high professional skills. It is also necessary to provide assistance in the process of choosing a profession that is suitable for the person from among related professions.

The scientific literature presents technologies and tools for methodological aspects of the professional socialization of students of future teachers. One of them is the 78-question “Interest Map” method of A.E. Golomshtok. [4.P.192] This method is aimed at identifying students’ professional interests through test questions. This test was reworked several times by the St. Petersburg Institute of Psychoneurology and other authors. As a result, the 144- and 174-question versions of this method were applied to pedagogical practice. Also, such tasks as professional psychography and a professional choice sheet are widely used.

E.G.Goziev puts forward the conclusion that “all pedagogical activities (external influence) in choosing a profession serve to realize the student’s professional identity and make a conscious choice of a profession, while the process of realizing his professional identity (internal influence) proceeds on the basis of psychological laws” [5.P.14].

Sh.D.Zhamgurova interpreted the choice of profession and its socio-psychological foundations as follows: “choosing a profession requires a comprehensive analysis of factors, parents, students’ peers, their own personal positions, attitudes, orientation, value system, and ideas about professions.”

One of the pressing problems in the process of professional formation of students is the issue of attitude towards professional activity. The system of professional relations and professional-cultural relations includes:

- self-oriented orientation;
- activity-oriented orientation;
- people-oriented orientation.

The psychological foundations of the formation of professional cultural relations in students are:

- high prestige;
- high economic security;
- creativity, active social relations;
- self-development;
- striving for advancement;
- spiritual satisfaction;
- preservation of identity;
- labor activity;
- education system;
- family life;
- social sphere;
- a circle of interests.

Preparing future teachers for the activities of professional socialization of students requires mastering the basics of initial professional culture. Professional culture always embodies the spiritual basis that shapes it, which consists of a symbolic expression of ideas, knowledge and human goals. It is impossible to form a professional culture without ideas, knowledge and goals. The product of spiritual culture manifests itself only in material form, is thus materialized and applied to social and professional activities. If we explain the essence of

professional culture more clearly, then any of its external manifestations reflects the level of development or maturity of a person.

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